

inoculum containing about 10^8 cells/ml. Disease intensity was scored after 14 d, using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scale.

Only RP2151-173-1-8, RP2151-40-1, Kachamota, and DV85 showed resistance to the Aduthurai pathotype (Table 2). □

Field and screenhouse evaluation for resistance to rice tungro (RTV)

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We evaluated high-yielding rice varieties and lines for field tolerance to RTV in the 1985 wet season. Infection was scored 30 d after transplanting and field tolerance was scored after flowering.

Varieties and lines scoring 1 to 3 were tested in the screenhouse in the 1986 wet season, with 20 seedlings/variety exposed to either 1 or 5 RTV-viruliferous leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* per seedling. Symptoms were scored and seedlings tested for presence of the bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses by latex serological test. Infection rate and plant height and tiller number reduction were scored visually.

Virippu and Ptb 18 scored 1 in the field but had high infection in the screenhouse (see table). Some varieties showing field tolerance had high infection in the screenhouse. Reduction in height and tiller number was less in varieties with field tolerance score 1 than in varieties with score 3.

Infection with both RTBV and RTSV was low in these varieties. Some had RTBV alone. RTSV infection alone was low (0-10%). Ambemohar 59, BJI, and Gopalbhog were not infected with either virus. Infection and reduction in height and tiller number were higher in plants inoculated at 5 hoppers/ seedling.

Although Utkalprabha and Sabari had high infection in the field, by time of flowering they showed tolerance scores of 2 and 3. □

RTV incidence in rice varieties in the field (1985 wet season) and in a screenhouse test (1986 wet season). Cuttack, India.

	Field		Screenhouse ^b		
	Symptoms (%)	Tolerance score ^a	RTBV+RTSV (%)	RTBV (%)	RTSV (%)
<i>Popular Indian varieties</i>					
Ambemohar 59	0	1	0	0	0
Basmati 370	2	1	0	10	0
Krishnabhog	3	1	0	10	0
Mudgo	0	1	0	10	0
Ptb 18	0	1	0	60	0
Tulsimanjari	2	1	0	10	0
Type 90	2	1	0	20	0
Virippu	6	1	0	30	10
Amaravathi	0	2	10	30	0
BJI	0	2	0	0	0
Gopalbhog	4	2	0	0	0
Pokkali	7	2	10	30	0
Utkalprabha	25	2	20	50	0
Vytilla 2	2	2	10	30	0
White Luchai	5	2	10	20	0
Asha	18	3	10	0	0
Aswathi	3	3	10	20	0
Daya	15	3	10	20	10
Ratna	8	3	0	20	0
Sabari	51	3	10	10	0
TN1 (check)	100	9	80	0	0
<i>CRR breeding lines</i>					
CR146-7001	2	1	0	10	0
CR146-7004	15	2	10	20	0
CR260-131-5-713	12	2	10	30	0
CR316-639	6	2	0	20	0
CR365-134	9	2	10	20	0
CR319-644	6	3	10	0	0
CR260-136-321	7	3	10	20	0

^a1 = no visible symptoms; 2 = plants are green, slightly stunted, less than 10% did not flower; 3 = less than 20% did not flower; 9 = plants show orange yellow color, severe stunting, and no flowering.

^bMass inoculation at 5 leafhoppers/seedling. All varieties except two had 0 RTSV: Virippu and Daya had 10% RTSV. LSD for the screenhouse symptoms was 17.83 (0.05) and 24.07 (0.01).

Reactions of Mahsuri and Sona Mahsuri to blast (BI)

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Mahsuri rice covers a substantial area during the Jul-Dec season in Assam

State. But it is highly susceptible to neck BI. We are looking for a variety with Mahsuri-type grain and resistance to neck BI.

Sona Mahsuri (KMS5914-4-6) from the cross Sona/ Mahsuri (released in Karnataka State as Mandya Vijaya), with panicle traits similar to Mahsuri, is moderately resistant to leaf BI. We compared leaf and neck BI reactions of Sona Mahsuri and Mahsuri.

Table 1. Leaf and neck BI reactions^a of Mahsuri and Sona Mahsuri. Assam, India.

Variety	Leaf BI		%	Neck BI	
	Score	Reaction		Score	Reaction
Sona Mahsuri	4	MR	18.1	5	MR
Mahsuri	7	S	97.4	9	HS
Pusa 2-21, susceptible check	8	S	98.5	9	HS

^aMR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Table 2. Yields of Mahsuri and Sona Mahsuri, Assam, India.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (kg/1.6 m ² plot)
Mahsuri	98	1
Sona Mahsuri	92	1

Two rows of 28 hills of each variety, divided by one row of susceptible check Pusa 2-21, were grown. Leaf Bl was scored by *The standard evaluation system for rice*. Neck Bl was recorded as percent affected panicles on 10 random hills. Yield was measured at a B1-free site.

Sona Mahsuri was moderately resistant to both neck Bl and leaf Bl (Table 1). Mahsuri was susceptible to leaf Bl and highly susceptible to neck Bl. Grain yields were on a par, but Sona Mahsuri matured 1 wk earlier than Mahsuri (Table 2). □

Screening new rice selections for reaction to major diseases

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We evaluated 18 stabilized lines from the rice improvement program and 18 released cultivars for leaf blast (Bl), neck Bl, sheath rot (ShR), and grain

discoloration (Gld) at the Agricultural Research Station, Ponnampet, (hot spot for B1 disease in rice) during 1986 wet season.

Selections from Pusa 150/IR36 and Pusa 150/IM 1 were resistant to leaf B1 (see table). Neck B1 infection was lowest in IR20, Karuna, and Jaya.

Selections from Jaya/Mahsuri were free of ShR infection. Maximum infection was in Pragathi and selections of Jaya/Type 3.

Jaya, IR20, and Jaya/ Mahsuri derivatives had the most Gld. Mahsuri, Intan Gowri, and Prakash had none.

Karuna and selections from Pusa 150/IM 1 showed combined tolerance for all four biotic stresses. □

Incidence of leaf B1, neck B1, ShR, and Gld. Ponnampet, Karnataka, India, 1986 wet season.

Entry	Leaf blast ^a	Neck B1 incidence (%)	ShR infection (%)	Gld (% affected)
Pusa 150/IR36	0	44.1	3.3	5.0
Pusa 150/IM-1	0	22.2	23.0	1.0
Karuna	0	10.2	6.8	1.0
Mahsuri	1	46.8	14.5	0.0
Intan Gowri	1	52.9	23.5	0.0
Jaya	1	14.0	19.8	25.0
Intan mutant 1	1		Wiped out by neck B1	
IR20	2	7.4	9.3	25.0
Pusa 150/Tellahamsa	2	29.6	4.3	5.0
Jaya/Type 3	2	70.2	36.2	5.0
Mandya Vijaya	2		Wiped out by Bl	
Puspha	2	17.0	13.2	1.0
IET7031/Mangala	3	74.1	6.9	11.0
Pusa 150/Sona Mashuri	3	81.9	4.6	1.0
Nandi	3	87.0	5.7	1.0
Mahsuri/IR36	3	77.6	22.4	5.0
Prakash	4	33.7	18.6	0.0
Rasi	4		Wiped out by Bl	
Jaya/Basmati	4	55.8	1.9	5.0
Mandya Vani	5	45.1	31.4	10.0
ES18	5		Wiped out by Bl	
Jaya/Mahsuri	5	68.8	0.0	20.0
Jaya/IET7031	5		Wiped out by Bl	
Madhu	6		Wiped out by Bl	
Pragathi	6	41.9	39.6	10.0
Naga	6	76.2	20.6	1.0
Mangala	7		Wiped out by Bl	
IET7031/Tellahamsa	7	60.9	23.2	5.0
Sharavathi	7	72.1	27.9	1.0
Jaya/ Halubbulu	7		Wiped out by Bl	
Pusa 150/Basmati	7		Wiped out by Bl	
Intan	9	10.2 ^b	2.6 ^b	2.0 ^b
Tellahamsa	9		Wiped out by Bl	
Mahsuri/Doddy	9		Wiped out by Bl	
Karikagga/Halybbulu	9		Wiped out by Bl	
Arkavathi	9		Wiped out by Bl	

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale 0-9. ^bFrom side tillers.

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Bacterial blight (BB) development in rice varieties and screening tests

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Genetic resistance appears to be the only feasible method of managing BB in the tropics and subtropics. In most screening tests, leaves are clip-inoculated with the local isolate of the pathogen at maximum tillering stage, with disease rated 15 d after inoculation (DAI). Total uniformity in the stage of plant growth, vigor, microclimate, amount of inoculum applied, and the mechanism of disease development in test varieties is difficult to achieve.

We evaluated inoculated plants against a wider spectrum of environmental conditions by rating disease in test varieties twice—15 and 35 DAI.

Some varieties expressed the maximum measurable response to *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*